

Vocal Riffs Model for Synthesis and Transformation

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Abstract

Singing voice is one of the most challenging musical instruments to model. For decades, much research and study has been performed in order to synthesize and imitate it. The fruit of this labor was a large number of synthesizers. Among all these approaches, the sequential concatenation of samples from a database is the one that had most success. However, it has some weak points regard to the flexibility and expressivity. In addition, current systems designed for voice samples transformation, such as: transposition, time-scaling, or resampling, among others, may cause a decrease in sound quality, and they do not allow lyrics modification.

The goal of this thesis is to model, synthesize and transform Vocal Riffs: short rhythmic, melodic, or harmonic vocal figures charged of personality that provides the singer taste to a song. The modeling process extracts high level features from the target Vocal Riff and stores them as a template in a database. This template can be directly synthesized or transformed in order to create new Vocal Riffs. The software aspires to not lose sound quality during the transformation process, since the transformation is applied to the features in the template, instead of being applied to the sample. Furthermore, this fact allows other singing voice aspects to be modified, such as the lyrics, and provides flexibility to the usage of Vocal Riffs.

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Introduction

Motivation

For decades, much research and study has been performed in order to understand the mechanisms involved in singing voice production. This is probably the most complex musical instrument and the richest one, with regard to expressivity. Thus, the research in the field of sound synthesis has put a special emphasis on the imitation and the reproduction of this expressiveness.

Among all existing techniques for the singing voice synthesis, the one which has had the most success is the sequential concatenation of samples from a database. The strong point of this method is the simplicity. It is also characterized by the naturalness of the synthesized output, since the samples used are real sounds. Nevertheless, it has some weak points such as a lack of flexibility and expressivity.

This approach could be used for synthesizing a really wide range of musical sounds, even the singing voice. These techniques are used in Vocaloid software made by Yamaha through the collaboration of the Music Technology Group of the Universitat Pompeu Frabra from Barcelona.

This thesis deals with creating and modeling Vocal Riffs for enhancing the Vocaloid singing synthesis. A Vocal Riff is defined as the "short rhythmic, melodic, or harmonic figures charged of personality that provides the singer taste to a song" [1]. It is possible to synthesis this using the sample based synthesized for including it in Vocaloid composition; nevertheless, proper setting the riff pitch curve or dynamics evolution could be a long and hard process. Thus, the usual process for including vocal riffs is turning to Vocal Riffs libraries such as Vocalplanet, by Spectrasonics.

However, the inconvenience of these commercial libraries is that the riffs could not be

modified or adapted to the user's taste. Actually, plug-ins or software that use samples libraries (Gigasamples, etc.) allow some sample modification, such as: transposition, time-scaling, resampling,.. Even in software like Melodyne it is possible to carry out note segmentation and transform the sample by modifying the notes. Nevertheless, current software does not allow modifying the lyrics. The main motivation for this project was to implement software able to (1) create a database from the riffs the user was interested in, and (2) transform the riffs using high level controls providing great flexibility and high quality. For achieving this, the software uses Vocalistener [2], which provides a means for easily creating Vocaloid scores which resemble the Vocal Riffs.

Objectives

The objective of the thesis is to model Vocal Riffs for building a database of high level features (instead of sound samples), synthesize Vocal Riffs from the features stored and allow several transformations for creating new Vocal Riffs. Thus, a software, that includes the functionalities required for this objective, has been implemented:

1. Implement a template creator able to extract features required for the further synthesis and transformation. This engine would be able to extract the information and store it in a organized way inside a template.
2. Implement a synthesis engine able to convert the features extracted by the template creator into an audio file ready for being used in a musical composition.
3. Implement a template transformer able to modify the features of the template, and allow create different riffs from the original.

A part from the implementation work, there is some other research work to be performed:

1. Check the good performance of several source separation algorithms. The results of this study would be useful for the implementation of a source separation module that allows to use polyphonic riffs as an input of the system.
2. Study different methods of modeling and synthesizing vibrato. This tool would allow to change the parameters of the vibrato present of the riffs stored in the database, providing to the transformer new functionalities not present in the current audio softwares.

Organization of the thesis work

This thesis is organized in several chapters. In this introduction the motivation of the work has been explained, and the context in which all the research has been carried out was introduced.

Next, in Chapter 1 the proposed software will be introduced, with a detailed explanation of its different modules and the scripts generated during its implementation.

In Chapter 2, the set of features extracted from the audio samples and stored in the Vocal Riffs database will be introduced. These features are the information required to resynthesize or transform a Vocal Riff. In addition, this section will describe the steps taken to compute each feature, the problems encountered, and the solutions proposed.

Chapter 3 is focused on the synthesis engine. The methods and all data required for carrying out the synthesis of the riffs from the template database are explained in this chapter.

As we mentioned, one of the most valuable features of the proposed software is the capability of modify the templates once they are stored in the database. This is accomplished thanks to the template transformer module. This module is going to be described in Chapter 4. The description will focus on the process of transformation of each feature separately.

Finally, the document ends with Chapter 5, which includes all conclusions extracted from the work and some further research that could be done for following the line of study of singing voice synthesis, feature extraction and voice transformation.

Chapter 1

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed software would basically automatically extract some features. These features would compose the template that would be stored in the database, and later they would be used for resynthesizing or transforming the riff for including it in a musical composition. In figure 1.1 This template is consisted of the following features:

Figure 1.1 shows the general block scheme of the proposed system, it can be noticed that there are three main blocks that compose all of the performance of the proposed system. The template creator is responsible for the high level feature extraction coming from the inputs. At the end of this process, the original template is created. This template consists of the following features:

- Note segmentation.
- Pitch and duration of each note.
- Lyrics (phonetic transcription of the riff).
- Dynamics info.
- Vibrato characteristics, in the case that the riff would contain vibrato that could be modeled.

Due to some problems that may happen during the extraction of certain features, the process is not completely unsupervised; there are some tasks that have to be performed by the user which will be commented on in Chapter 2. Once the original template is

Figure 1.1: General block diagram of the proposed system.

created, there are two possibilities. On one hand, the template can be synthesized and it can be included in a composition. For synthesizing it, the synthesis engine will take the template and will render a wave file. The synthesis engine is explained in Chapter 3.

On the other hand, if the user wants to modify some features for adapting the riff, the template is modified using the transformer module. This module allows the user to modify the features desired taking advantage of a visual and intuitive interface. When the transformations are performed, the user can store the new template and synthesize it using the synthesis engine. Examples of modifications could be pitch transposition, lyrics changing or the modification of vibrato parameters extracted during the template creating process. All transformer functionalities are going to be explained in Chapter 4.

Chapter 2

TEMPLATE CREATOR

The template creator is the module responsible for feature extraction. For complete extraction, the template creator is composed by different modules: (1) the pitch module that has the objective of pitch extraction (using the YIN algorithm) and fixes the possible estimation errors that may appear, (2) dynamics extraction from the original riff, (3) estimation of the vibrato parameters (this is optional; the input sound may not have a vibrato), (4) the lyrics transcription required for the synthesis engine, and (5) setting of the phonemes' durations. The complete block diagram of this module is presented in figure 2.1.

This chapter will explain each one of the sub-routines that compose the entire system. These sub-systems are going to be analyzed bellow. First of all, it will be detailed all the inputs and outputs.

2.1 Inputs

The template creator uses as inputs the audio sample, the lyrics transcription and the note segmentation (this can be observed in figure 2.1):

- The audio samples could be extracted from a music plus vocals recording or acapella vocals. In the first case (music + vocal), the system would require a source separation block for separating the vocals from the background music. This procedure will be explained in further sections.

Figure 2.1: Block scheme of the feature extractor system

- The lyrics transcription should be done manually or automatically. Despite the existence of algorithms that could transcribe the lyrics of an audio excerpt, the transcription performed in this case would be carried out manually.
- The note segmentation is also done manually, using audio analyzers. Nevertheless, as for the lyrics transcription, the segmentation could be done automatically using one of the several scripts that exist at present. The incorporation of automatic transcriber and note segmenter tools will be mentioned in further work.

2.2 Ouputs

The output file of the template creator is the template itself. As the complete system is implemented in Matlab, we took advantage of the data types of this environment, and decided to store all features extracted in a Matlab structure (*.mat). The following scheme, describes the hierarchy of the template and the different fields that compose it.

- **Template**
 - **Name:** This is the name of the riff for being identified.
 - **Fundamental frequency (f0)**
 - * *Pitch:* Pitch samples of the riff.
 - * *Time:* Time stamp of each sample of the pitch curve.
 - **Dynamics**
 - * *Pow:* Power envelope samples.
 - * *Time:* Time stamp of the dynamics samples.
 - * *Dyn:* Dynamics samples of the riff.
 - **Trans**
 - * *Phon_map:* This is an structure that stores the phonetic mapping. It is a Mx4 cell-type structure, where M is the number of the phonemes. The first column corresponds to the phoneme. The second and third column is the phoneme starting and ending time stamp respectively. And the last column is the flag that indicates the note the phoneme belongs to.
 - **Vibrato**
 - * *Vibrato:* Samples of the modeled vibrato.
 - * *Novibrato:* Samples of the pitch curve related to the vibrato removal.
 - * *Depth:* Depth parameter of the vibrato.
 - * *Rate:* Rate parameter of the vibrato.
 - * *Notes_vib:* Is a 1xM matrix, where M is the number of notes. And is set to 0 when the note has not vibrato and set to 1 when it has it.
 - * *Time:* Is a 1x2 matrix. Indicates the starting and ending time of the vibrato.

Besides the creation of the final Template, other output files are created. These files are related with the synthesis process required for dynamics estimation process, which consists on the comparison of the original power envelope with the provision synthesis of the riff using provisional dynamics until both power envelopes became similar; because of this, the auxiliary files that the synthesis engine requires also have to be created during the template creation process. The detailed explanation of these files is placed in the chapter dedicated to the synthesis process (Chapter 4).

2.3 Subsystems and scripts

Figure 2.1, shows a block diagram of the entire system. Each subsystem is drawn using a different color, in order to distinguish them better. The subsystem related to the power is colored in red, the one related to the pitch variation is in orange, and the subsystem related to the lyrics processing is showed in blue.

Mainly, it is possible to separate the sub-systems according to the inputs they have. On one hand, we have the dynamics and pitch sub-system that requires the temporal signal of the riff. On the other hand, the phonemes sub-system depends on the lyrics transcription and the manual note segmentation.

At first, the dynamics estimation subsystem is based mainly on the computation of the power envelope of the temporal signal, and then it is used the Vocalistener [2] method for converting power into dynamics. In the case of the pitch estimation, the YIN algorithm [3] is used for estimating the fundamental frequency using the riff sound signal as an input. Nevertheless, this method has some weaknesses that are going to be explained in the following section. Some errors in the estimation may appear that have to be fixed. Once the pitch is fixed, the user has the possibility of using the vibrato modeler for estimating the parameters of the possible vibratos that were in the riff. This estimation is mainly performed by the user who has to manually select the points of the vibrato, and then the scripts automatically calculates all the parameters: depth, phase and rate. Finally, the phonemes sub-system is responsible for the lyrics transcription and the time adjusting of each of the phonetic symbols.

Once all these routines are performed, all the features are stored in the template, which is ready for being transformed or synthesized for use in musical compositions.

Next, the subsystems introduced are going to be explained in-depth.

2.4 Phonemes transcriber

The phoneme subsystem is responsible for processing the incoming phonetic information of the riff. This whole process is summarized in figure 2.2.

The inputs required by the phoneme processing subsystem are the lyrics transcription of the riffs and the note segmentation (notes duration in seconds), as was mentioned above.

Figure 2.2: Block scheme of the phoneme subsystem

The first process that is performed is the transcription of the lyrics into phonemes. For achieving this, the standard of the University of Edinburgh is used. The Unisyn lexicon [4] is a master lexicon transcribed in keysymbols, a kind of metaphoneme which allows the encoding of multiple accents of English¹.

The lexicon is accompanied by a script which transform the base lexicon (in English) via phonological and allophonic rules, and other symbol changes, to produce an output transcription. In this case, the output is displayed in SAMPA.

These scripts were developed by the Music Technology Group of the Universitat Pompeu Fabra from Barcelona, and were implemented in the python language. This script also includes a duration calculus of each of the phonemes that comprise the lyrics of the riff. The rules applied for the computation of the phonemes' minimal duration are based on D.H. Klatt's studies [5], and later reviews by M. Goto [6]. The minimal durations define the minimal length of a phoneme which can be understood properly.

When the lyrics are transcribed into phonetic symbols with computed durations, a re-adjustment of the durations has to be carried out. Typically, a riff's notes' durations are longer than the minimal duration computed in the previous step; because of this a script was designed exclusively for this thesis: the adjuster. The adjuster is responsible for adapting the minimal duration of each phoneme to the required for filling the complete length of each syllable.

The input of it are the minimal lengths obtained previously, and the output is the new lengths, that fulfill the whole duration of each syllable. The script is implemented in MATLAB. The remaining duration is added to the vowel in the syllable. For detecting the vowel phonem inside a syllable, a phonetic dictionary is used (implemented in python). In the inverse case, when the sum minimal duration of the phonemes in a syllable is shorter than the note duration, these are reduced proportionally for fitting the desired duration.

¹This prototype is created just for English vocal riffs, as an start for further research

2.5 Pitch estimation

This subsystem is responsible for the extraction of the pitch evolution of the original riff. Due to some limitations in the process of the pitch estimation, this could not be carried out in a unsupervised way.

The figure 2.3 represents a block diagram of the processes applied to the pitch.

Figure 2.3: Scheme of the processes related to the pitch estimation and correction.

2.5.1 Pitch Corrector

This script is based in MATLAB language and it also implements a visual interface for better interaction with the user.

The objective of this subsystem is to fix the possible errors caused in the pitch estimation process. The YIN algorithm designed by Cheveigné [3] is the script used for pitch estimation. Once pitch evolution is obtained, it is plotted so the user can observe the fragments where the estimation has not been performed properly. At this point, it has to be mentioned that it is possible to deal with two types of errors: octave errors and voiced/unvoiced fragments.

The YIN algorithm operates in the frequency domain and it uses the autocorrelation method for finding periodicity in the spectrum. An octave error is caused by an incorrect estimation of the fundamental caused by assuming one of the harmonics is the fundamental. This may happen when the actual fundamental is masked temporally.

The voiced/unvoiced error is caused by the presence of certain noisy phonemes such as /s/, /f/ and /z/ and also silences. Another cause may be the singing style, if the original

riff sung using rough voice, typical in rock or jazz style. The spectrum in these cases is noisy and not harmonic at all, so it is very difficult to estimate the fundamental. The aperiodicity, is an indicator for determining inharmonic fragments of the signal. The higher value, the less harmonic spectrum. This indicator could be used for automatically detecting voiced/unvoiced errors; nevertheless, this process has to be done manually in this prototype, and it is suggested that this be an improvement for further research. Under conditions, the output of the algorithm is a very unstable curve that has to be fixed for a proper synthesis of the riff.

In the following figure 2.4, it is possible to observe this mistakes.

Figure 2.4: Example of errors during the pitch estimation using YIN algorithm.

In figure 2.4, is possible to observe the immediate output of the pitch estimation using YIN algorithm. Voiced/unvoiced errors caused by the silence are squared in red, voiced/unvoiced errors caused by noisy phonemes, in this case /j/ are squared in purple and octave errors are marked in orange.

Each error has its own solution. The pitch fixer is the script responsible for the fixing of each one of the different problems. It is implemented using the Matlab language and is launched immediately after the pitch estimation.

Firstly, the voiced/unvoiced error is fixed just by erasing the fragment and completing the curve by using spline interpolation methods. The process applied to octave error sections could be the same, but for keeping the curve shape it was thought to design a different one.

In the case of the voiced/unvoiced errors, the output is not related to the actual shape of the curve, it is just related to fluctuations due to lack of periodicity in the spectrum; on the other hand, in the case of octave mistakes, the curve has the same shape as the real one, but in a different pitch height. Thus, the solution for this problem is to modify the pitch by adding or subtracting the surplus or the missing pitch to from the wrong estimated fragment, for obtaining a continuous curve.

The figure 2.5 shows the pitch curve once these processes are applied, and the comparison with YIN's output. The purple curve represent the curve estimated by the YIN algorithm, in blue is presented the correction performed by pitch corrector.

Figure 2.5: Comparison of the YIN's output with the pitch curve obtained after the correction process.

The figure 2.5 shows the pitch curve once these processes are applied, and the comparison with YIN's output. The purple curve represent the curve estimated by the YIN algorithm, in blue is presented the correction performed by pitch corrector.

It is possible to observe that, as it was mentioned above, the shape is kept in those fragment that existed an octave error, and it was not kept for the voiced/unvoiced section. After executing these scripts the pitch curve is continuous and smother, so it is ready for being stored in the template. An example of a complete pitch correction is shown in figure 2.6. The smoothness of the pitch curve is important for synthesize understandable and clear riffs.

Figure 2.6: Final pitch curve after the pitch fixer process is performed.

2.5.2 Vibrato modeler

The Vibrato Modeler is the subsystem in charge of vibrato features extraction. Those features are depth, rate and phase.

When the pitch correction is finished, the user has the option of performing a vibrato model or skipping this step. It has to be remembered that the vibrato model is an optional part in the template creation. If the original riff does not present a vibrato on it, it is not necessary to execute this script. On the other hand, if the riff has a vibrato and the user is interested in changing the parameters of this vibrato, it is useful to use this tool. Another option is including a vibrato fragment in riffs without it. Anyway, there are a lot of possibilities and it all depends on the user's goals.

This script was also implemented exclusively for this thesis. The model first requires a supervised step; the user has to manually choose the points of the vibrato fragment, beginning point, ending point, peaks and valleys. The system automatically computes the period between peaks and it creates the modeled curve using sines and cosines. An example of this process can be observed in figure 2.7,

Each of the samples that compose the vibrato has one associated depth and rate value. The depth function is the interpolation of the depth value computed at the peak/valley points of the vibrato (black points in 2.7). The depth at these points of maximum amplitude is

Figure 2.7: Analysis process of the vibrato. Peak/valleys manually selected

the difference between the pitch curve (vibrato) and the no-vibrato curve (the definition of the no-vibrato curve is explained below). Once the depth at these points is computed, the rest are interpolated. The rate is constant within a half period. In figure 2.7, the black rectangles represent the half periods of the sinusoids that compose the vibrato model. The samples that belong to the half sinusoid that models the vibrato have the same rate equal to the inverse of two times the length (in time) of the rectangle. In figure 2.8 it is possible to observe that extracted rate (in the lower plot) is a non-continuous function. This process is acceptable as a first step, but if we want to change the duration of the rate, the vibrato parameters should be continuous. Therefore, the script ends with a re-adjustment of the parameters.

The transformation from discrete to continuous is achieved by interpolating the original (discontinuous) rate function. After the interpolation the curve will require a phase correction, since the method used is spline. This is needed for assuring that the instantaneous phase in the peak position (and valleys) was a multiple of $\pi/2$, so that the cycle ends in the correct position, and the final model has no discontinuities. The phase correction consists of integrating the value of the continuous rate function in a period and computing the difference between the proper multiple of $\pi/2$ at each peak. After this procedure the function remains as it is shown in figure 2.9.

At the same time, the no-vibrato curve is estimated, which corresponds to the pitch curve

Figure 2.8: Parameters extracted from the analysis of the vibrato.

if the vibrato was removed. This is computed by keeping just the middle points between a peak and a valley, and then interpolating the rest of the values. This procedure can be observed in figure 2.10. In figure 2.10, the black points represent the information used for interpolating the no-vibrato curve. These correspond to the middle point between a peak and a valley (the beginning and ending points are also included in the no-vibrato information that will be interpolated).

As mentioned above, the user can select whatever peaks and valleys he/she is interested in. In figure 2.11 an example of a free vibrato model is presented. The objective of this could be the creation of a vibrato model that is not present in the original sound, or to fix a badly estimated vibrato, caused by one of the problems commented in the pitch estimation.

2.6 Dynamics estimator

Dynamics are very important in music, they give more expressivity to the song, and in this case to the riffs. This script uses the input sound signal for estimating the dynamics. From this signal, the power envelope is extracted, which is the feature most related to the dynamics. Nevertheless, a post-processing step is required for converting energy in

Figure 2.9: Discontinuous rate obtained in the first step (red) and interpolated continuous rate obtained in the final step (blue).

dynamic values (for us values normalized between 0 and 1, where 0 means whispering and 1 means shouting).

In order to achieve this, the Vocalistener method proposed in [2] was used. This consists of estimating the dynamics through an iterative process which consists of two steps:

- **Boot Stage:** the dynamic value is a number between 0 and 1. The boot stage consists of synthesizing the audio using 4 different values of constant dynamics. The values chosen are 0, 0.3, 0.6 and 1. After the synthesis, we obtain four signals with constant dynamics, and we are able to create a dynamics mapping by relating the value of the power envelope of the synthesized signals and the dynamics used for synthesizing them. So as a first step we can select the dynamics of each sample that are closer to the original power value. Nevertheless, if we finish here, the dynamics values are restricted to just four. In order to improve this fact, we perform the Optimization stage.
- **Optimization stage:** this part is the iterative one. Once we obtain an approximate dynamic curve, in this stage, the curve is optimized for fitting over the target by following an iterative process. In our case, the number of iterations is six. The values are obtained by averaging the dynamics value that most closely approximates

Figure 2.10: No vibrato model.

the target power envelope. Then, the sound is synthesized again using the dynamics obtained after this iteration and iteratively, the curve would fit to the target one.

Procedure of the dynamics estimation explained above is represented in the block diagram of the 2.12.

In figure 2.13 the output plot from this script is presented. In the upper plot, the power envelopes of both signals, synthesized and original are shown. The lower plot depicts the dynamics obtained from this process. We can notice that the result is quite satisfactory; the power envelope of the synthesized sound fits almost perfectly in the original power envelope.

2.7 Source separator

The objective of the source separation module is adding more freedom to the vocal riffs source selection. Without this module, the vocal riffs that can be modeled, transformed and synthesized using the proposed software are restricted to vocal a cappella recordings. Concerning to the pitch extraction method, YIN algorithm is a monophonic pitch

Figure 2.11: Free vibrato model.

extractor, so if we try to extract the pitch from a signal that contains voice plus musical accompaniment, the curve obtained would not correspond to the pitch curve of the instrument we are interested in: the singing voice. Pre-processing has sense for having the capability of creating templates from riffs that are present in commercial recordings.

The procedure carried out is based on [7]. The process consists of applying a bidimensional pass band filter to the signal according to frequency and panning dimensions. The user should adjust the frequency and panning parameter in order to keep just the vocals. When the vocals are separated, it is possible to execute the features extractor. It has to be mentioned that the source separation worsens the quality of the YIN algorithm performance. Furthermore, due to the fact that the separation process is a frequency filtering, some harmonics or fundamentals may be erased (especially, when high pass filtering is performed for separating the bass guitar). This could cause many octave errors. In addition, if some instruments remain in the separated signal, the pitch estimated becomes less stable (this process would include more aperiodic fragments) and problems would appear, similar to the voiced/unvoiced errors explained previously.

In this case, the solution is already implemented in the pitch fixing; nevertheless, in this case the process becomes more difficult because of all the additional problems that the voice separation causes. Thus, the reduction of this pitch errors depends on the quality of the separation; the better separation the less complication in the pitch repairing.

Figure 2.12: Block diagram of the dynamics estimation process

Another aspect we have to take into account is the power. It could happen that after the separation, there are some remains of the drum set. The percussion has an important presence in terms of energy. Because of this reason, and due to how the dynamics estimation tends to adapt perfectly to the original power envelope, some peaks may appear at the dynamics curve, for example, when the kick is played. As these peaks correspond to the energy of the instrumental part, they should not be considered in the vocal's dynamics extraction. In order to fix this, a script has been designed that works in the same way as the aperiodic fragments fixing. It consists of pointing out the segments where the dynamics were leaked from other sources (dynamic peak), and automatically, the dynamic curve would be interpolated for erasing the extra power present in the separation.

In the procedure explained above, the user has to do the separation process before launching the software. The user should use the separated signal as an input. However, we have tested another algorithm, also included in MONET project, that extracts automatically the pitch of the singing voice from a polyphonic sound. The output pitch is stored in a text file codified in ASCII. The prototype was modified in order to allow this input, and obtain a more accurate pitch estimation. So it is possible to skip using the YIN algorithm. Nevertheless, the audio signal is also required for computing the dynamics computation.

Figure 2.13: Upper. Power envelope of the target signal (red) and last iteration synthesis (blue). Lower. Dynamics obtained.

Chapter 3

TEMPLATE SYNTHESIS

The synthesis method is a process required for converting the template to an audio file. It is also required for the dynamics estimation process in the template creator.

The synthesis engine used for this project was the Vocaloid synthesizer developed by Yamaha and explained in [8]. This process is based on the concatenation of vocal samples (diphonemes) from a database. This concatenation may cause some discontinuities between samples used in the library. The discontinuities are fixed by transforming the samples and compose a continuous trajectory inside the sonic space.

The synthesis engine of this software is controlled by a Matlab script, that performs some data pre-processing and makes several calls to python routines. The Vocaloid synthesis implementation that it is being used, requires an XML file with the information about pitch, dynamics, durations and lyrics of the riff. For achieving this, the Matlab main routine execute the following steps:

- The first step consists of extracting the information that is going to be included in the XML file from the template. Once the data is extracted from the template, the creation of four output files is required which will be the input of XML Builder. There are four output files:
 - Riff_name.f0 : This file encodes the pitch information in ASCII code as an $M \times 2$ matrix, where M is the number of pitch information samples (depending on the length of the vocal riff). The first column provides the time stamp of each sample and the second column determines the pitch value of each sample.

- Riff_name.dyn : This file encodes dynamics info. This data is structured in the same way as the pitch info. As there is not the same amount of pitch and dynamics info, it is required to include a time stamp info in this file too. So this file is also structured in a $M \times 2$ matrix, where M is the number of samples of dynamics.
 - Riff_name.phon : This file has the phonetic info. In other words, it stores the phonetic symbols of the riffs. It consists of a row matrix ($1 \times N$, where N is the number of phonetic symbols). The complete phonemes of the riffs also includes the first and last silence of the riff, so an example of a phon-file is: "Sil o 5 r a l t Sil". This info is also in ASCII code.
 - Riff_name.dur : As a complement to the phonetic info, this file provides the time stamp of each one of the phonemes that compose the riff lyrics. It is used also ASCII code for coding a $M \times 2$ matrix, where M is the number of phonemes (including the first and last silence of the sentence). The first column corresponds to the starting time of the phoneme and the second to the ending time.
- Once the data is properly organized, it creates the output files that would require the XML Builder. This script is implemented in python and it reads the files for composing the XML file.
 - Finally, when the XML-file is created, the main routine launches the synthesis engine which renders the output synthesized riff in wav-format. The data used for the synthesis is stored in a different database that the one that has the voice sound samples. These samples will be transformed and concatenated for composing the synthesized signal.

Chapter 4

TEMPLATE TRANSFORMATION

The model and synthesis process of the template creation ends when all features are fixed and stored in the database; nevertheless, it was decided to develop a visual interface dedicated to the transformation of the template, this is the Template Transformer. The objective of this module is to provide the user the right tools to customize and create new templates from the ones built from the audio files.

The transformation tools provided by the interface are:

- Lyrics modification.
- Dynamics modification.
- Note duration modification.
- Pitch modification (global or note-by-note).
- Vibrato parameters modification.

All these types of transformations are done in a parallel way (see figure 4.1, which shows the block diagram of the template transformation module) and thanks to the preview buttons it is possible to listen to the original riff, the synthesized riff, and the riff modification synthesis, in order to appreciate the transformations and compare them with the original riff. The main interface is shown in 4.2, and it is going to be described below.

Figure 4.1: Block diagram of the Template Transformer module.

4.1 Lyrics transformation

For lyric transformations, it is required to the user to write the new lyric in the text box and the click on UPDATE LYRICS. Then the transcription script, described in Chapter 2, would be executed again for computing the new phonemes, with the new durations. Furthermore, the lyrics in the pitch plot would be updated, for a clear view of the phonemes' temporal evolution. The part of the interface responsible of this process is shown in figure 4.3.

4.2 Dynamics transformation

Dynamics transformation is performed note-by-note. The interface plots the temporal evolution of the dynamics divided by vertical lines that indicate the ending of one note and

Figure 4.2: Template transformer interface.

Figure 4.3: Lyrics transformer interface.

the beginning of the following one. When the user clicks on one note, this would become grey (also in the pitch plot); this means that the note is selected for being changed. For increasing (or decreasing) the dynamics of the selected note, it is required that the user sets the variation of dynamics that is going to be performed in the text box. Once this amount is set, the user has to click on DYNAMICS UP, if the objective is to increase the dynamics, or, in the opposite case, DYNAMICS DOWN, if the objective is to decrease them. The controls of the dynamics are shown in figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Dynamics transformer interface.

The dynamics have a normalized value between 0 and 1. If the increasing or the decreasing of the dynamics causes the curve to go above 1 or below 0, the software would show a saturated curve with 1 and 0 as a maximum and minimum values respectively. However, internally the software would keep the original shape (curve with values below 0 and above 1) in order to make this process reversible.

4.3 Note duration transformation

The software allows the modification of the duration of the notes. The way of changing it is by varying the rectangle control in the pitch plot. These rectangles are able to change the size and the position; We will only explain the size transformation by now, since a combined transformation would cause a combined change of pitch and duration. This is going to be explained in the next section.

The process does not add new information (new samples) to the pitch curve. The effect of this transformation is changing the temporal axis and the time references of the pitch samples (that are included in XML file for the synthesis). In parallel, the temporal reference of the dynamics info is also changed, because they do not have the same number of samples.

In figure 4.5 it is possible to observe an example of a duration changing. The fourth note is lengthened, and the other notes maintain their durations. The grey rectangles shows the original status of the notes when the riff template was loaded. These are useful for comparing the modified riff to the original situation. In addition, the reset button on the control panel will return the riff to the original state, original values of lyrics, pitch and dynamics.

Figure 4.5: Note duration transformer interface.

4.4 Pitch transformation

Pitch transformation could be performed globally or note-by-note. The buttons GLOBAL UP and GLOBAL DOWN control the global pitch. The amount of increasing/decreasing pitch has to be set in the textbox; this parameter is configurable and it is in octaves. In figure 4.6 the elements for controlling this transformation are presented.

Figure 4.6: Global pitch transformer interface.

In this case, the global pitch has been increased by a half octave. As in the previous transformation, the grey rectangles present in the pitch plot indicate the original position of the notes.

The other option, the modification of the pitch of a certain note (note-by-note), is carried out by dragging the note to the pitch desired. Each note is represented by an empty rectangle at a certain height (this corresponds to the average pitch of the note). So, the height modification of this rectangle would change the average pitch of the note if the movement is vertical.

Changes in the height, consist on an addition/substraction of a certain value of pitch on each of the samples that comprise the note. This variation will cause a discontinuity in the edges of the note. For achieving a continuous curve, an extra process for maintaining the continuity of the pitch is required.

In order to fix this gap, a transition window was defined, so as to perform a smooth solution. The size of the transition window could be set by the user in the proper menu. This menu may be observed in figure 4.7

One option was to remove all pitch information inside the window and to interpolate the remaining content. This option would cause the erasure of the shape of the pitch curve around the border of the note. Therefore, an alternative method was designed that consists on applying a gradual function. An example of this function is defined in figure 4.8

The function is created automatically and its maximum and its minimum, that coincide with the border between notes, are plus and minus the half of the pitch gap respectively. Another characteristic of this function is that it could be asymmetric. In other words, it is not required to have the same samples in the first and the second part. Finally, it has to be mentioned that while in one of the discontinuities (between the modified note and

Figure 4.7: Transition window configuration interface.

Figure 4.8: Transition function.

the previous one) the function is applied, the discontinuity created between the modified note and the following is fixed using the negative function ($-\text{tranfun}(x)$). The result of the pitch modification of a certain note is shown in figure 4.9. In this case, the pitch of the fifth note has been modified from G2 to E3.

Regarding the discontinuities, the interface allows showing or hiding the pitch curve without the gap fixing. If the check button (in the plot control panel) is enabled, the discontinuities are shown. In figure 4.10 is possible to observe the interface presenting the unfixed discontinuities (using a fairer color) and the correct pitch curve on top. This is useful for the user to check the transformations done, to verify that the modifications are correct, as well as to be sure that the original pitch shape has been kept.

Figure 4.9: Note-by-note pitch transformation interface.

Figure 4.10: Discontinuities fixed in deep blue. The fair blue curve represents the pitch evolution without fixing the discontinuities.

The system also allows horizontal movements. In the case that the movement was to the left, the system would make the previous note shorter and reallocate the current note and the following notes. In the other case, if the movement is to the right, the software would make the previous note longer, and allocate the active note and the following later in time (keeping their durations). In any case, the movement of the active note, without changing its size (duration) would be translated to its reallocation, and the modification of the duration of the previous note.

4.5 Vibrato transformation

In the same panel used for setting the transition windows, there are two extra options: "Modeled Vibrato" and "No Vibrato". The first option would show the pitch curve of the riff but change the vibrato section to a modeled one. As with the original pitch, this curve could be changed in duration and pitch height. One of those changes would change the other curves (original vibrato and no vibrato curve).

The parametric vibrato is modeled using the equation 4.1. As it can be seen in the expression, there are some variables that could be changed: the rate and the depth. This is possible by modifying the values in the textboxes of the interface (figure 4.11).

$$f'_o(n) = \overline{f}_o(n) + A(n)\sin(\sum 2\pi f(n)\Delta_t + \varphi(n)) \quad (4.1)$$

where, f'_o represents the vibrato model (pitch curve), $\overline{f}_o(n)$ the no vibrato curve, $A(n)$ is the depth of the n-th sample, $f(n)$ is the rate of the n-th sample, Δ_t the temporal increment of the vibrato and $\varphi(n)$ is the phase corrector introduced in Chapter 2 that assures a phase value of a multiple of $\pi/2$ at the peak/valley points.

This interface and the visualization of the vibrato model curve can be observed in figure 4.11. The curve in green color indicates the user that it corresponds to the modeled one, the blue curve represents the original one, and the red curve shows the vibrato erased curve.

Figure 4.11: Vibrato model interface.

As an extra help, in the side of the interface there are two plots that are enabled when a note with a vibrato on it is selected. They represent the temporal evolution of the depth and the rate of the vibrato. The temporal axis of these plots are normalized to the duration of the vibrato. Values are from 0 to 1, where 0 means the beginning of the vibrato and 1 the ending.

Figure 4.12 shows a modeled vibrato with the parameters changed. The system just allows the scaling of the parameters, so the original parameters would be represented by 1, and

2 would correspond to the double of the original parameter. In the case of the figure 4.12, the depth was scaled by 2, and the rate by 1.7.

Figure 4.12: Vibrato model interface with the original parameters changed. Depth scaled by 2 and rate scaled by 1.7.

Finally, the other option, the no vibrato curve, represents the pitch curve with the vibrato erased. The removing process, that was explained in previous sections, is shown in figure 4.13.

Figure 4.13: Removed vibrato pitch curve.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

Once the system was finished and tested with several riffs, the results seemed to be acceptable, but improvable. As a conclusion, the template creator, transformer and synthesizer are very useful tools for the creation of vocal riff databases that could be used in musical compositions.

Firstly, using this method, it is possible to skip the current riff design process. Using the YIN estimation it is possible to estimate the pitch evolution quickly and with an acceptable accuracy. It has to be said that we are on the way to achieving more quality in the Vocal Riffs analysis and model; as proposed in the further work section. Furthermore, the Vocalistener method saves much time regarding the current manual dynamics definition: as it is an unsupervised process, the original dynamics are computed automatically.

Secondly, this tool allows the user to create riff templates of self-recordings. This is very useful if the user does not find the proper riff that fits in the composition. In this case, the user can record a riff and then create the template using this software. This saves the time dedicated to searching for the proper riff in existent databases, and also he/she is able to add transformations to his/her own riff. The riffs included in the demo reproduced during the presentation of this thesis (and stored in the database created by the system) are from different sources. A group comes from the VocalPlanet library (a cappella), another ones are coming from the Source Separation Module implementation (less quality in the pitch estimation), and another group comes from the analysis of riffs recorded explicitly for this thesis. All of these riffs were analyzed by the Template Creator, transformed by the Template Transformer and synthesized by the Synthesis Engine.

Regarding the creation of Vocal Riffs with source separation techniques, the analysis process in this case is harder than the one performed for a cappella riffs, but the result is worthy. Using this option it is possible to create templates from riffs present in famous recordings, and thus give the taste of the user's favorite singer to the composition. In order to perform this process correctly, the separation method has to be improved. This is a very interesting point that is going to be taken into account in the further research.

Finally, the transformation engine provides the flexibility that the user requires to adapt the database riffs to the musical piece, regarding lyrics, pitch, dynamics or vibrato parameters. The transformation of musical samples commonly causes a loss in the audio quality, but in the case of this module the interesting point is that it allows maintaining the audio quality, which is just related to the quality of the modeling. This is a very important aspect to take into consideration. A simple and intuitive interface has been developed that makes the transformation process easier.

5.1 Further research

As mentioned below, there is more work to be performed.

First of all, there is some work to be done regarding the source separation tool. The separation engine has to be improved for making the pitch fixing stage easier, which is the critical point of this type of riff modeling. As an alternative to the algorithm used in the source separation, we are still working on a research line for automatically extracting the pitch curve of the main instrument (singing voice) in a polyphonic signal, which would allow not to use the YIN algorithm.

Secondly, the modeling process has some unsupervised duties to be carried out, which require the user interaction, such as: note segmentation, lyrics detection and pitch error fixing. Further work will improve these processes in order to avoid the user supervision in the model. Further research in the automatic note segmentation and lyrics detection also is going to be undertaken. Furthermore, the aperiodicity indicator will be the key concept to work on, to convert the pitch fixer in an unsupervised process.

Furthermore, much work could still be performed in order to improve the modeling process. The implementation of more accurate methods of analysis and modeling of Vocal Riffs would increase the quality of the audio created by using this software.

There are plans of carrying out a test for comparing the synthesized riffs created using the

template creator with riffs created manually by the usual way using the Vocaloid interface. After this test we could conclude if the estimation and quality of the synthesis using this system is comparable to the quality (or fidelity to the original riff) of the riffs designed using the traditional way. If this is true, this system would be worthy and would save time and effort regarding the riff modeling. Thus, the objectives about modeling, transforming and synthesizing riffs without losing audio quality would be accomplished.

Finally, there is the possibility of porting the system to another environment in collaboration with the R&D Center of Yamaha in Hamamatsu (Japan).

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